

PHYSICOCHEMICAL PRETREATMENT OF AGRO-WASTE PEELS FOR IMPROVED HYDROLYSATE SUGAR DELIVERY

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Abstract

Physicochemical pretreatment of some food and fruit peel agro-wastes using different mineral acids and bases was done to identify common bench reagents that have good hydrolytic effect on the observed substrates. The reagents considered were H₂O, 1% NaOH, 1% KOH, 1% Ca(OH)₂, 1% H₂SO₄, 1% HCl and 1% HNO₃. The substrates studied were pineapple peels, banana peels, plantain peels, cassava peels, yam peels, potato peels and rice husk. It was observed that the substrates have target chemicals for optimum pretreatment or hydrolysis. Results also showed that 1% NaOH was the best reagent with a cumulative hydrolysate sugar weight yield of 17.97%. This was followed by 1% H₂SO₄ with a percentage cumulative hydrolysate sugar weight yield of 17.55%. Others were 1% HCl, 1% HNO₃, 1% KOH, H₂O, and 1% Ca(OH)₂ with a percentage cumulative hydrolysate sugar weight yield of 17.39%, 14.82% 13.31%, 10.02% and 8.86% respectively. The hydrolysate sugar weights achieved from the considered substrates were substantial and made them suitable to be utilized for fermentation.

Keywords: Physicochemical pretreatment, agro-wastes, mineral acids and bases, cumulative hydrolysate sugar weight yield

1. INTRODUCTION

Renewable raw materials from various lignocellulosic biomass types are presently being utilized as renewable raw materials for bioethanol production. This is sequel to fossil fuel depletion and environmental problems associated with fossil fuel usage. Lignocellulosic biomass is composed of cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin, as well as other minor components. Both the cellulose and hemicellulose fractions are polymers of sugars and potential fermentable sugars sources (Harmsen *et al.*, 2010). Delignification of lignocellulosic biomass is done using various chemical, physicochemical

and biological pretreatments (Singh *et al.*, 2016). The purpose of the pretreatment is to remove lignin, expose the hemicellulose, and reduce cellulose crystallinity. A pretreatment step is also necessary for a successful enzymatic hydrolysis process (Alessandra *et al.*, 2012). A good pretreatment procedure is expected to improve the formation of sugars or the ability to subsequently form sugars through enzymatic hydrolysis; avoid the degradation or loss of carbohydrate and be cost-effective (Sun and Cheng, 2002).

This work aimed to investigate the efficacy of different mineral acids and bases in the pretreatment and hydrolysis of some food and fruit peel agro-wastes. A combined chemical

and mechanical pretreatment procedure was adopted in hydrolyzing these substrates. The cumulative hydrolysate sugar weight yields from the seven considered reagents were compared. The results of this study may help to establish some common and cost-effective pretreatment reagents that are effective in the hydrolysis of some readily available agro-wastes.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample Preparation for Pretreatment

The food items were purchased from Uselu Market, Benin-City, Nigeria. They were washed with distilled water, air-dried and their peels collected. Rice husk was obtained from a processing mill at Abakiliki, Ebonyi State, Nigeria. The fresh peel samples were cut to sizes of about 3-5cm in length prior to further treatments.

Physicochemical Pretreatment

Chemical hydrolysis was performed concurrently with mechanical comminution. 15g of the substrate in each case was mechanically comminuted in a high-speed blender with 100ml of each of the following listed reagents for 5 minutes: (1) H₂O, (2) 1%

NaOH, (3) 1% KOH, (4) 1% Ca(OH)₂, (5) 1% H₂SO₄, (6) 1% HCl and (7) 1% HNO₃.

Thereafter, the mixture was filtered and the hydrolysate sugar content of the filtrate was analyzed using a high precision Brix refractometer. Further hydrolysis was recorded after the first step of physicochemical pretreatment when the broth was incubated for 10 minutes at 120°C after the first step of mechanical comminution.

Measurement of Sugar Level

A high-precision refractometer (Grand-index with automatic temperature compensation) was used to analyze the substrate's hydrolysate sugar levels in degree Brix (Maroulis *et al.*, 2003).

In a typical measurement, a drop of the sample was put on the glass surface of the refractometer and the sugar level was subsequently determined. The results in degree Brix were subsequently converted to weight of sugar using equation (1):

$$\text{Weight of hydrolysate sugar (g/L)} = \text{°Brix} \times \text{Specific gravity} \times 10 \quad (\text{Robert, 2003}). \quad (1)$$

The obtained results from the physicochemical pretreatments are shown in Tables 1 – 7.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Pretreatment

Table 1: Weight of Hydrolysate Sugars (g/L) from the Pretreatment of Pineapple Peel Waste

Pineapple Peels		
Pretreatment Conditions	Initial Weight after blending (g/L)	Final Weight after incubation (g/L)
15g/100ml of H ₂ O	20.2	26.3
15g/100ml of 1% NaOH	28.3	48.9
15g/100ml of 1% KOH	28.3	34.5
15g/100ml of 1% Ca(OH) ₂	23.2	28.3
15g/100ml of 1% H ₂ SO ₄	33.4	43.7
15g/100ml of 1% HCl	33.4	39.6
15g/100ml of 1% HNO ₃	29.3	38.6

The results in Table 1 show that 1% NaOH was the best pretreatment reagent for pineapple peels having the best hydrolytic effect as seen from the hydrolysate sugar weight. 1% NaOH was the best of the alkalis while 1% H₂SO₄ was the best of the acids. H₂O gave the least hydrolysate sugar yield.

Table 2: Weight of Hydrolysate Sugars (g/L) from the Pretreatment Banana Peel Waste

Banana Peels		
Pretreatment Conditions	Initial Weight after blending (g/L)	Final Weight after incubation (g/L)
15g/100ml of H ₂ O	18.1	23.2
15g/100ml of 1% NaOH	33.4	42.7
15g/100ml of 1% KOH	28.3	37.5
15g/100ml of 1% Ca(OH) ₂	18.1	22.2
15g/100ml of 1% H ₂ SO ₄	28.3	40.6
15g/100ml of 1% HCl	30.4	41.7
15g/100ml of 1% HNO ₃	27.3	39.6

Table 2 shows that 1% NaOH was the best pretreatment reagent having the best hydrolytic effect as seen from the hydrolysate sugar weight. This was followed by 1% HCl and 1% H₂SO₄. 1% Ca(OH)₂ gave the least hydrolysate sugar yield.

Table 3: Weight of Hydrolysate Sugars (g/L) from the Pretreatment of Plantain Peel Waste

Plantain Peels		
Pretreatment Conditions	Initial Weight after blending (g/L)	Final Weight after incubation (g/L)
15g/100ml of H ₂ O	28.3	36.5
15g/100ml of 1% NaOH	44.8	61.4
15g/100ml of 1% KOH	38.6	48.9
15g/100ml of 1% Ca(OH) ₂	28.3	34.5
15g/100ml of 1% H ₂ SO ₄	38.6	52.0
15g/100ml of 1% HCl	38.6	54.1
15g/100ml of 1% HNO ₃	38.6	51.0

Table 3 shows that 1% NaOH was the best pretreatment reagent for ripe plantain peel waste having the best hydrolytic effect as seen from the hydrolysate sugar weight. This was

also followed by 1% HCl and 1% H₂SO₄. 1% Ca(OH)₂ gave the least hydrolysate sugar yield.

Table 4: Weight of Hydrolysate Sugars (g/L) from the Pretreatment of Potato Peel Waste

Potato Peels		
Pretreatment Conditions	Initial Weight after blending (g/L)	Final Weight after incubation (g/L)
15g/100ml of H ₂ O	19.1	47.9
15g/100ml of 1% NaOH	48.9	59.3
15g/100ml of 1% KOH	28.3	49.9
15g/100ml of 1% Ca(OH) ₂	18.1	28.3
15g/100ml of 1% H₂SO₄	32.4	69.8
15g/100ml of 1% HCl	32.4	68.8
15g/100ml of 1% HNO ₃	28.3	68.8

Table 4 shows that 1% H₂SO₄ was the best pretreatment reagent for potato peel waste having the best hydrolytic effect as seen from the hydrolysate sugar weight. This was followed by 1% HCl and 1% HNO₃; both having the same hydrolysate sugar weight. 1% Ca(OH)₂ also gave the least hydrolysate sugar yield.

Table 5: Weight of Hydrolysate Sugars (g/L) from the Pretreatment of Cassava Peel Waste

Cassava Peels		
Pretreatment Conditions	Initial Weight after blending (g/L)	Final Weight after incubation (g/L)
15g/100ml of H ₂ O	13.1	26.3
15g/100ml of 1% NaOH	48.9	59.3
15g/100ml of 1% KOH	28.3	48.9
15g/100ml of 1% Ca(OH) ₂	18.1	26.3
15g/100ml of 1% H ₂ SO ₄	28.3	63.5
15g/100ml of 1% HCl	28.3	65.6
15g/100ml of 1% HNO ₃	25.2	56.2

Table 5 shows that 1% HCl was the best pretreatment reagent for cassava peel waste having the best hydrolytic effect as seen from the hydrolysate sugar weight. This was

followed by 1% H₂SO₄ and 1% NaOH. Both H₂O and 1% Ca(OH)₂ gave the least hydrolysate sugar yield

Table 6: Weight of Hydrolysate Sugars (g/L) from the Pretreatment of Yam Peel Waste

Yam Peels		
Pretreatment Conditions	Initial Weight after blending (g/L)	Final Weight after incubation (g/L)
15g/100ml of H ₂ O	13.1	20.2
15g/100ml of 1% NaOH	38.6	48.9
15g/100ml of 1% KOH	22.2	33.4
15g/100ml of 1% Ca(OH) ₂	14.1	23.2
15g/100ml of 1% H₂SO₄	23.2	51.0
15g/100ml of 1% HCl	23.2	48.9
15g/100ml of 1% HNO ₃	20.2	47.9

Table 6 shows that 1% H₂SO₄ was the best pretreatment reagent for yam peel waste having the best hydrolytic effect as seen from the hydrolysate sugar weight. This was followed by 1% HCl and 1% NaOH; both gave the same sugar weight yield. H₂O gave the least hydrolysate sugar yield.

Table 7: Weight of Hydrolysate Sugars (g/L) from the Pretreatment of Rice Husk Waste

Rice Husk		
Pretreatment Conditions	Initial Weight after blending (g/L)	Final Weight after incubation (g/L)
15g/100ml of H ₂ O	15.1	56.2
15g/100ml of 1% NaOH	61.4	104.0
15g/100ml of 1% KOH	45.8	61.4
15g/100ml of 1% Ca(OH) ₂	14.1	48.9
15g/100ml of 1% H ₂ SO ₄	25.2	93.2
15g/100ml of 1% HCl	21.2	92.2
15g/100ml of 1% HNO ₃	18.1	87.9

Table 7 shows that 1% NaOH was the best pretreatment reagent having the best hydrolytic effect as seen from the hydrolysate sugar weight. This was followed by 1% H₂SO₄ and 1% HCl. 1% Ca(OH)₂ gave the least hydrolysate sugar yield. The above results from Table 1 to Table 7 indicated that these substrates have target chemicals for optimum pretreatment or hydrolysis.

Table 8: Percentage Cumulative Hydrolysate Sugar Weight Yield from the Considered Substrates and Reagents

	HSW (g/L) H ₂ O	HSW (g/L) 1% NaOH	HSW (g/L) 1% KOH	HSW (g/L) 1% Ca(OH) ₂	HSW (g/L) 1% H ₂ SO ₄	HSW (g/L) 1% HCl	HSW (g/L) 1% HNO ₃
Pineapple Peels	26.3	48.9	34.5	28.3	43.7	39.6	38.6
Banana Peels	23.2	42.7	37.5	22.2	40.6	41.7	39.6
Plantain Peels	36.5	61.4	48.9	34.5	52.0	54.1	51.0
Potato Peels	47.9	59.3	49.9	28.3	69.8	68.8	68.8
Cassava Peels	26.3	59.3	48.9	26.3	63.5	65.6	56.2
Yam Peels	20.2	48.9	33.4	23.2	51.0	48.9	47.9
Rice Husk	56.2	104.0	61.4	48.9	93.2	92.2	87.9
Cumulative HSW (g/L)	236.6	424.5	314.5	211.7	413.8	410.9	350.4
% Cumulative HSW yield	10.02	17.97	13.31	8.97	17.52	17.39	14.82

HSW = Hydrolysate Sugar Weight, % Cumulative HSW yield = (Cumulative HSW/ Total Cumulative HSW) * 100%

The bar chart shows the percentage cumulative hydrolysate sugar weight yield from the considered agro-waste peels using common bench reagents. It shows the percentage contribution of each reagent on the overall hydrolysis. It was observed that

considerable amounts of hydrolysate soluble sugars were liberated during the physicochemical pretreatment. 1% NaOH, 1% H₂SO₄ and 1% HCl were best in hydrolyzing the substrates though they seemed to be chemically selective. 1% NaOH gave the best

hydrolysate sugar weight result for sugar-based substrate peels (ripped pineapple, ripped banana and ripped plantain peels) and rice husk while 1% H₂SO₄ gave the best result for starch-based substrate peels of yam and potato. 1% HCl was the best for cassava peels. Water and 1% Ca(OH)₂ were both unimpressive in the physicochemical pretreatment test. Cumulatively, 1% NaOH was the overall best reagent with a cumulative hydrolysate sugar weight yield of 17.97%. This was followed by 1% H₂SO₄ with a cumulative hydrolysate sugar weight yield of 17.55%. Others were 1% HCl, 1% HNO₃, 1% KOH, H₂O, and 1% Ca(OH)₂ with cumulative hydrolysate sugar weight yield of 17.39%, 14.82%, 13.31%, 10.02% and 8.86% respectively.

4. CONCLUSION

The results from this study provided evidence that readily available agro-waste peels of no commercial value can be hydrolyzed to fermentable sugars using common readily available bench reagents. The generated fermentable sugars can be utilized in bioethanol production and other industrial applications.

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